

**THE POWER OF QUESTIONING: RHETORICAL QUESTIONS AS A
PERSUASIVE STRATEGY IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH POLITICAL
DISCOURSE**

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**SAVOL BERISH KUCHI: INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK SIYOSIY DISKURSIDA
ISHONTIRISH STRATEGIYASI SIFATIDAGI RETORIK SAVOLLAR**

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**СИЛА ВОПРОСА: РИТОРИЧЕСКИЕ ВОПРОСЫ КАК
УБЕДИТЕЛЬНАЯ СТРАТЕГИЯ В УЗБЕКСКОМ И АНГЛИЙСКОМ
ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОМ ДИСКУРСЕ**

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***Abstract:** Rhetorical questions are a powerful tool in political speeches, influencing public opinion and reinforcing ideological messages. This study compares their use in English and Uzbek political discourse, highlighting their role in persuasion, audience engagement, and discourse coherence. By analyzing a selection of political speeches, the research identifies key pragmatic functions of rhetorical questions and examines how linguistic and cultural factors shape their effectiveness. The findings reveal that while rhetorical questions serve similar*

persuasive purposes across both languages, their frequency, structure, and impact vary depending on cultural and rhetorical traditions. The study contributes to a fundamental analysis of political rhetoric and provides insights into how rhetorical questions shape discourse strategies in different linguistic contexts.

Annotatsiya: Ritorik savollar siyosiy nutqlar uchun ta'sir doirasi kuchli bo'lgan stilistik vosita hisoblanadi. Ushbu izlanish Ingliz va O'zbek siyosiy diskurslarida ritorik savollardan ishonitirish, auditoriya bilan chiqisha olish hamda nutq izchilligi maqsadlarida foydalanilishini chog'ishtiradi. Tanlab olingan siyosiy nutqlar tahliliga asoslanib, tadqiqot ritorik savollar ishtirokining muhim pragmatik vazifalarini aniqlashtiradi va samaralilikni belgilashda lingvistik-madaniy asoslarni ko'zdan kechiradi. Topilmalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, har ikki diskursda ham ritorik savollar bir xil ishonitirish maqsadlari uchun xizmat qilsa ham, ularning tez-tez qo'llanilishi va tuzilmasi farqlanadi. Ilmiy izlanish siyosiy-lingvistik stilistikaning fundamental tahliliga hissa qo'shadi va har xil lingvistik kontekstlarda ritorik savollarning diskurs tuzilmalarini qanday shakllantira olishi bo'yicha bir nechta tushunchalarni ta'minlaydi.

Аннотация: Риторические вопросы являются мощным инструментом в политических выступлениях, оказывая влияние на общественное мнение и укрепляя идеологические послания. В данном исследовании проводится сравнительный анализ их использования в английском и узбекском политическом дискурсе, с акцентом на их роль в убеждении, вовлечении аудитории и обеспечении связности речи. Путем анализа ряда политических выступлений выявляются ключевые прагматические функции риторических вопросов, а также рассматривается, как языковые и культурные факторы влияют на их эффективность. Результаты исследования показывают, что, несмотря на схожие убеждающие функции риторических вопросов в обоих языках, их частотность, структура и воздействие различаются в зависимости от культурных и риторических традиций. Данное исследование вносит вклад в фундаментальный анализ политической риторики и раскрывает, как риторические вопросы формируют дискурсивные стратегии в различных языковых контекстах.

Keywords: rhetorical questions, political discourse, pragmatics, persuasion, English, Uzbek, contrastive analysis, language and power.

Kalit so'zlar: ritorik savollar, siyosiy diskurs, pragmatika, ishonitirish, Ingliz, Uzbek chog'ishtirma tahlili, til va ta'sir kuchi.

Ключевые слова: риторические вопросы, политический дискурс, прагматика, убеждение, английский, узбекский, контрастивный анализ, язык и власть.

Introduction

Political discourse serves as a means of persuasion, aiming to shape public opinion, legitimize policies, and strengthen authority. Among the rhetorical strategies frequently utilized by politicians, rhetorical questions play a crucial role—not to seek responses but to reinforce arguments, stimulate thought, and challenge opposition. This study explores the pragmatic significance of rhetorical questions in English and Uzbek political speeches, examining their function in influencing public perception and structuring discourse.

Materials and Research Methods

In political discourse, rhetorical questions enhance persuasion by steering audiences toward intended conclusions while preventing counterarguments. They highlight main points, captivate listeners, and strengthen ideological positions, adding impact and authority to political messaging. Cornelia Ilie has conducted an extensive research on pragmatic values of rhetorical questions and defines them as a type of question that do not seeks actual answers but serve specific communication goals. According to Ilie, they play a key role in shaping discussions and arguments by reinforcing a speaker's viewpoint, expressing emotions, or influencing an audience. Unlike genuine questions, which expect informative responses, rhetorical questions are used to emphasize a point or guide the listener toward a particular interpretation. Ilie's research highlights how these questions function in different settings, such as political speeches and courtroom debates, showing their power as persuasive tools.¹

Mara Frascarelli, another contemporary linguist, has contributed to the understanding of rhetorical questions through her research on discourse and syntax. In her work, she explores how certain lexical items can shift an interrogative from a standard question to a rhetorical one, influencing the interpretation and interaction within a conversation. This perspective highlights the syntactic and pragmatic mechanisms that differentiate rhetorical questions from genuine inquiries, emphasizing their role in asserting viewpoints or guiding the listener's perspective.² Persuasion, on the other hand, depends on the speaker's effective use of rhetoric. In classical antiquity, rhetoric was defined as *ars bene dicendi*—the art of speaking well in public. This implies that some individuals are more skilled speakers than others, a belief reflected in debates, political discussions, and even social media arguments. The most effective rhetoric is measured by audience response, ultimately influencing decisions like voting in democracies. Conversely, rhetoric fails when the audience

¹ Ilie, C. *What Else Can I Tell You? A Pragmatic Study of English Rhetorical Questions as Discursive and Argumentative Acts*. Almqvist & Wiksell International., 1994.

² Frascarelli, M. The commitment of rhetorical questions. *Glossa: a journal of general linguistic.*, 2018. –P. 1–46.

rejects the speaker's message. Generally, together with most stylistic devices, rhetorical questions play a crucial role to set standards and manipulate the audience with power dynamics as well. This study uses a contrastive qualitative approach to examine how rhetorical questions function as persuasive tools in Uzbek and English political speeches. The data includes speeches, debates, and interviews from well-known politicians over the past 20 years. Key political events, such as election campaigns and parliamentary debates, were selected to ensure relevance. Rhetorical questions were identified through purposive sampling, focusing on their role in influencing audiences. The analysis is based on discourse and pragmatic studies, exploring how these questions shape power dynamics and engagement. A cross-linguistic comparison highlights similarities and differences between Uzbek and English political discourse.

Results

It is presented special excerpts from political speeches in Uzbek and English, analyzing how rhetorical questions function within their discourse. The findings highlight differences and similarities in their usage, structure, and persuasive impact across both languages. Focusing on English political discourse it is estimated that the role of rhetorical questions is valid and has some exact functions. In his election victory speech in 2024, Donald Trump used the notable instance which shows his unprecedented nature of political movement: *“We overcame obstacles that nobody thought possible and it is now clear that we've achieved the most incredible political thing, look what happened, is this crazy?”*³

The rhetorical question *“Is this crazy?”* is likely used to highlight the surprising and extraordinary nature of Trump's campaign success. Instead of expecting an actual answer, the question encourages the audience to think and agree with his point, making his message more persuasive. In the contrastive analysis, it could be mentioned a difference with Uzbek political discourse in terms of the style of the rhetoric language. In his speech, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M.Mirziyoyev, at the meeting with the representatives of the Uzbek sports delegation who participated in the XXXIII Summer Olympic Games in Paris used a special rhetorical question, which helps to reach the public encouragement, delightfulness and the feeling of patriotism: *Boks bo'yicha milliy terma jamoamiz oltin medallar soni bo'yicha mamlakatimiz tarixida Olimpiya o'yinlari rekordini yangiladi va umumjamo'a hisobida 1-o'rinni egalladi. Erkaklar o'rtasida yettita oltin medalning beshtasini – e'tibor bering, beshtasi – yoki 71 foizini bizning bokschilarimiz qo'lga kiritdilar. Bu – chinakam jasorat va bahodirlik namunasi*

³ <https://www.whitehouse.gov/remarks/2025/02/remarks-by-president-trump-before-cabinet-meeting/>

emasmi?! Bu – Yangi O‘zbekiston tarixining chinakam yangi sahifalari emasmi?!⁴

It is concluded that by using rhetorical questions, Sh.M.Mirziyoyev does not seek an actual response but rather reinforces a sense of unity and accomplishment among his audience. The table below presents a contrastive analysis of rhetorical questions used in Sh.M.Mirziyoyev’s and D.Trump’s speeches, highlighting differences in formality, purpose, and audience engagement.

Aspect	Shavkat Mirziyoyev’s Speech	Donald Trump’s Speech
Formality and Style	<i>Formal and structured, using balanced parallelism.</i>	<i>Colloquial and informal, appealing to spontaneity.</i>
Purpose and Effect	<i>Celebrates a national achievement, reinforcing unity and historical significance.</i>	<i>Highlights the unexpected nature of his victory, creating surprise and excitement.</i>
Audience Engagement	<i>Affirms a shared belief, leaving little room for doubt.</i>	<i>Invites the audience to reflect and agree, making them feel involved.</i>

Discussion

The findings reveal distinct patterns in the use of rhetorical questions within English and Uzbek political discourse. In English speeches, they serve to engage listeners in a conversational manner, encourage reflection, and challenge opposing views. In contrast, Uzbek political rhetoric employs them to strengthen national unity, inspire patriotism, and reinforce shared beliefs rather than stimulate debate. Furthermore, rhetorical questions in English tend to be sometimes spontaneous and informal, whereas Uzbek political speeches adopt a structured and formal approach, often using parallelism for emphasis. These variations stem from broader cultural and linguistic influences, where Western political discourse emphasizes interaction, while Uzbek rhetoric focuses on collective identity and leadership authority. Overall, while rhetorical questions function as an effective persuasive device in contexts, their role and influence are shaped by differing rhetorical traditions and sociopolitical frameworks.

Conclusion

Rhetorical questions are a key persuasive tool in political communication, though their usage varies across English and Uzbek discourse. While both employ them to influence audiences, English speeches use them interactively, whereas Uzbek rhetoric

⁴ <https://president.uz/oz/lists/view/7507>

focuses on reinforcing authority and national solidarity. These distinctions highlight the impact of linguistic and cultural frameworks on rhetorical strategies, offering insight into the broader dynamics of political persuasion.

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